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PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND FOREST BATHING AS TOOLS TO SUSTAIN THE BODY IMMUNE SYSTEM AGAINST COVID-19

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Abstract. Boosting immune system against COVID-19 is one of the weapons that can be used by people to protect their health in the worrying scenario due to the current pandemic associated to SARS-CoV-2. In this context, physical activity can be beneficial because triggers a number of biological processes in the human body that lead to increased levels of natural defenses against viral infections. If sport activities are performed in a green area the protective effects could be also higher as several plant species are natural emitters of biogenic volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that may in turn lead to immunostimulatory effects of potential utility to prevent or combat COVID-19. Herein, we analysed the scientific literature on both physical activity and 'forest-bathing' activity in relationship to COVID-19 aiming to bring new awareness about importance of practicing sport outdoors in a green area and of forest protection.

Keywords: immune system, physical exercise, SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, forest-bathing, biogenic volatile organic compounds.

Introduction. Acute viral respiratory infections are among the main infectious diseases affecting humans in the world. In 2020, a new disease caused by a coronavirus called severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), lead to the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), with a immunopathology similar to those of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) that originated in China but spread rapidly over the globe becoming a pandemic. More than 2,700,000 people died over the world and the pandemic is causing enormous problems from a sanitary and also economic point of view. While the world waits a mass immunization which could lead to a mid-term solution of the problem, provided that the virus variants will be effectively shielded by vaccination, and scientific research is exploring immediate solutions like effective therapies among the already known used to treat viral diseases and other COVID-19-related disorders (in an approach called 'drug repurposing'), the main lesson we learned by the COVID-19 disease is the importance of maintaining a healthy body. In fact, the key role of body immune system in contrasting viral diseases and in particular COVID-19 is well known but the lockdown measures undertaken from several government led people especially during first months of the pandemic to remain in their homes overeating and abandoning or strongly limiting their physical activities outdoors. In fact, with billions people in lockdown in the world, COVID-19 outbreak has often resulted in excessive sedentary time, especially in the elder population who seemed to forget the immune and cardiovascular beneficial

effects of exercise interventions in hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus and several other chronic disorders.

Objectives. Herein we aim to report the main information on the preventive role that physical activity plays in the fight against COVID-19. Moreover, we provide a perspective on the protective role of plant-emitted biogenic volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that can have immunomodulatory and antiviral effects. The ultimate goal of our work is the promotion of outdoor sport especially in parks and other places present in urban areas or naturally occurring that are rich in trees.

Materials and methods. In this work, we used a search strategy examining articles published between January 2020 and March 2021 with themes COVID-19 and physical activity, as well as COVID-19 and forest-bathing. The search was carried out on 19 March 2021. The databases searched were MEDLINE, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Google. Only studies reported in English were included.

Results. Practicing physical activity has modulatory effects on the immune system. In fact, sport exercise, leads to the increase of lymphocyte circulation, and release of several cytokines, and determines a lower impact and mortality of viral infections in people who practice sport regularly. Physical exercise leads initially to increased levels of type I interferons (IFN-I), whose response was found suppressed in COVID-19 patients, which drive the action of lymphocytes and macrophages, and is followed by lymphocyte action. Moreover, physical activity strengthens the immune system and leads to release of anti-inflammatory cytokines combatting the conditions determined in COVID-19 by lymphopenia and the storms of pro-inflammatory cytokines. [1] A direct link between chronic disorders like hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus and COVID-19 was recently reported. Since lockdown led most people, including hypertensive and diabetic patients, to limit their physical activities, this provoked a decrease in sport-related cardiovascular, and immune, benefits to the global population. Remarkably, physical activity may affect susceptibility to viral infections activating the autonomous nervous system and the resulting immunoregulatory hormones at the origin of the immune response and modifying the phenotype and levels of released cytokines, as well as the distribution of monocytes and lymphocytes. Not all levels of physical activities have the same protective effects. For example, heavy physical exercise, especially the intense and prolonged exercise in athletes, is associated with immune dysfunction, like suppressed salivary immunoglobulin, a release, lower activity of natural killer cells and reduced function of B- and T-cells and increased risk of illness, including infections of the upper respiratory tract. On the other side, moderate but regular physical activity induces immunomodulatory changes with shown benefits in prevention of cancer and cardiovascular disorders. From a quantitative perspective, in a study conducted on individuals performing low-volume exercise 15 min/day for 6 days a week showed for this group a reduced all-cause mortality by 14% and that associated with cardiovascular disease by 20%, compared to the inactive group. Owing to the immunomodulatory effect of exercise, improved anti-inflammatory responses, due to increased mitochondrial fatty acid oxidation, were observed in individuals with a sedentary lifestyle who underwent low-intensity exercise. Viral respiratory infections, including those associated to coronaviruses, induce severe inflammation, which is partially triggered by dysfunctions of the host's antioxidant defense. Interestingly, chronic and moderate physical activity reduced viral load and related disease severity in animal models of influenza virus infection, decreasing overall mortality and incidence rate and led to anti-

inflammatory effects higher than acute exercise. The antioxidant response stimulated by regular physical activity occurs via the Nrf2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2), a transcription factor involved in cardiovascular risk and antimicrobial defense. The high incidence rates of obese and overweight patients observed in COVID-19 patients who are in need of intensive care suggest that sedentary individuals, especially with pre-existing comorbidities including cardiovascular disease, hypertension, and diabetes have an increase risk to develop severe COVID-19. In this context, regular moderate physical activity is considered beneficial for preventing viral respiratory infection, including that due to SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus infection, and inflammation. [2] The type of exercise suggested in the recent literature for prevention of COVID-19 and other coronavirus-related diseases includes respiratory muscle training, aerobic and resistance training in healthy individuals. Patients with upper and lower respiratory tract illness should limit their physical activity to respiratory muscle training. In addition, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins C and D and regular consumption of fruit and vegetables is recommended to support the body immune system not only in the healthy, but also in patients affected by COVID-19.[3] In fact, not only movement but also nutrition plays a fundamental role in the prevention and management of the COVID-19. Even though evaluating dietary supplementation adopted to prevent or treat COVID-19 is difficult, a balanced diet including diverse micronutrients and sufficient amounts of macronutrients is considered optimal for boosting the immune system. On the opposite side, obesity and high-energy diets are major risk factors for a severe and fatal COVID-19. This suggests that body weight control is one of the most important preventive measures that everybody should undertake to prevent coronavirus diseases, together with reducing other lifestyle-related factors that impair regular immune functioning and the ability to overcome infections, such as alcohol intake and smoking.[4] Aside from adopting a correct life style, with a moderate but regular physical exercise, and a healthy nutrition program, spending time outdoors under the canopy of trees is another important measure to boosting our body immunity. Forests are enormously important for multiple aspects but mainly because they are a buffer zone separating humans and wild animals and when forests are lost, the chances of transmission of infectious diseases of zoonotic origin like COVID-19 increase significantly. [5] Not less important, forests are a precious source of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) which are endowed with biological effects on human health. The practice of spending time in a forests is known in Japan as 'forest-bathing' and is considered a therapeutic strategy to improve mind and immune system health. In a recent study we reported on clues about the lower COVID-19 impact in forested areas of Italy. Human exposure to high levels of fine particulate matter (PM) in the air of polluted (and tree-poor) areas of Italy, seemed to exacerbate the mortality due to COVID-19. On the other side, mitigating air pollution by intercepting PM onto plant surfaces and bolstering the human immune system by emitting bioactive VOCs, trees may exert a protective role reflecting in the lower mortality rate due to COVID-19 recorded in Italian regions with higher coverage by evergreen trees. Forests play a protective role by emission of immunomodulating VOCs and provision of dietary sources of antiviral compounds. [6]

Discussion. Staying at home, as recommended to people living in megacities in order to prevent the spread of the coronavirus, determined unintended consequences like overeating and being largely inactive, as well as an enhanced risk of infection and impaired immune function. Moderate but continuative exercise constitutes a feasible way of improving health, not only physical but also mental health, in the present time of anxiety and social isolation. Moderate physical exercise positively impacts the body immune system, counteracting age-associated

immune deficiency and reduces significantly the incidence of respiratory diseases. The location of the physical training programs, indoors or outdoors, is another important point to be assessed. Forest bathing is the practice of spending time outdoors under the canopy of trees with benefits on immune system as scientifically proven.

Conclusion. Based on the current scientific literature, regular but moderate physical activity through body weight maintenance may have benefits in regard to SARS-CoV-2 infection risk, and the management of the infectious disease. Overall, all the above features highlight the importance of practicing sport outdoors especially in green areas to bolster the body immunity thanks to the contributions given by physical exercise combined with the immunostimulatory effect provided by tree-emitted biogenic VOCs inhaled during movement.

References

1. da Silveira, M. P.; da Silva Fagundes, K. K.; Bizuti, M. R.; Starck, É.; Rossi, R. C.; e Silva, D. T. d. R., *Clinical and experimental medicine* **2020**, 1-14.
2. Jesus, I.; Vanhee, V.; Deramaudt, T. B.; Bonay, M., *Journal of Human Hypertension* **2021**, 35, (1), 1-3.
3. Khoramipour, K.; Basereh, A.; Hekmatikar, A. A.; Castell, L.; Ruhee, R. T.; Suzuki, K., *Journal of Sports Sciences* **2021**, 39, (1), 101-107.
4. Lange, K. W.; Nakamura, Y., *Movement and Nutrition in Health and Disease* **2020**, 4.
5. Sen, M, *Forests: at the heart of a green recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic* **2020**, 1-4.
6. Roviello, V.; Roviello, G. N., *Environmental chemistry letters* **2021**, 19, (1), 699-710.